

THE EFFECT OF SCHOOL CULTURE AND JOB SATISFACTION ON THE PERFORMANCE OF TEACHERS OF ILAGAN SOUTH DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

This study, completed in 2022, investigates the influence of school culture and job satisfaction on the performance of teachers in the Ilagan South District. Utilizing a descriptive-correlational research design, data were collected from 152 elementary school teachers using a validated questionnaire and their IPCRF ratings. Key variables included compensation, work environment, recognition, policies, and professional advancement. Results reveal that both job satisfaction and positive school culture significantly enhance teacher performance. Findings suggest that fostering collaborative practices and recognizing teacher efforts are central to improving instructional outcomes.

Keywords: *job satisfaction, school culture, teacher performance, professional advancement, workplace environment*

INTRODUCTION

Satisfied employees often reflect the presence of a strong organizational culture, which contributes significantly to institutional success. When employees are highly engaged and motivated, they tend to experience greater joy in their work, which positively influences their performance. However, the lack of a unified and consistently practiced culture may result in inconsistent behaviors, affecting overall job performance. On the contrary, employees who feel included and valued within their work environment are more likely to strive toward achieving organizational goals.

Organizational culture plays a critical role in shaping job satisfaction. Employees often recognize cultural elements such as collaboration, trust, and recognition as vital components that enhance their work experience. Therefore, many institutions intentionally develop organizational cultures to support employee satisfaction, promote retention, and build long-term commitment (Batugal & Tindowen, 2019; Cabigao, 2019).

Despite the complexity of defining culture, it remains a core component of organizational direction. A well-established culture acts as a compass, guiding employees' actions and reinforcing shared values and goals. Job satisfaction, meanwhile, is closely linked to job performance. Satisfied employees are generally more engaged, proactive, and resilient when addressing workplace challenges, resulting in improved organizational outcomes (Putra & Triatmanto, 2020; Lapien et al., 2020).

In the field of education, recent studies emphasize the influence of school culture and job satisfaction on teacher performance. A supportive school culture fosters collaboration and mutual respect, which enhances teacher morale and effectiveness. On the other hand, negative school environments can contribute to teacher stress, dissatisfaction, and underperformance (Al-Shammari et al., 2021; Aliazas & Elisa, 2021). When teachers feel supported and part of a cohesive work culture, they are more motivated and invested in delivering quality education (García-Carmona et al., 2019).

Moreover, job satisfaction among teachers is not solely determined by culture. It is also shaped by access to professional development, fair compensation, and positive working conditions. Teachers with adequate support systems are more likely to stay motivated, avoid burnout, and perform at higher levels (Manalo et al., 2020).

In the context of Ilagan South District, while many teachers express genuine passion for their profession, some still view teaching mainly as a financial necessity. Teachers frequently face financial strain, often resorting to salary loans to meet daily needs. Moreover, they experience stress from being given multiple administrative tasks, responsibilities that school heads sometimes have no choice but to delegate due to limited manpower or support staff. This added workload, coupled with leadership approaches that sometimes restrict open dialogue, contributes to fatigue and lower morale. Others also report diminished motivation due to the perceived lack of community involvement and support for local schools. These realities highlight the importance of examining how job satisfaction and organizational culture influence teacher performance within the district (Mercado, 2019; Kadtong et al., 2017).

This study aims to determine the effects of job satisfaction and organizational culture on teachers' job performance in the South District of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan.

Research Questions

This study addressed the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, years of service, and position?
2. What is the level of job satisfaction of the respondents in terms of compensation and benefits, working condition, interpersonal relationships, school policies and supervision, achievement and recognition, work itself, and responsibility and advancement?
3. What is the prevailing school culture in terms of teacher participation, goal clarity, management style, working relationships, and organizational commitment?
4. What is the level of job performance of the respondents in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment and diversity of learners, curriculum and planning, and assessment and reporting?
5. Do the respondents' profiles significantly affect their level of job satisfaction?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' profiles and their level of job performance?
7. Is there a significant effect of job satisfaction on job performance?
8. Is there a significant effect of school culture on job performance?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational design to investigate the relationship between school culture, job satisfaction, and teacher performance. The descriptive aspect was used to determine the profile of respondents, their levels of job satisfaction, school culture, and job performance. The correlational aspect explored the relationships among these variables without manipulating them.

Locale of the Study

The research was conducted in the Ilagan South District, Schools Division of the City of Ilagan, Isabela. The district has 15 schools, but the study focused on 14 elementary schools, excluding the Isabela School of Arts and Trades, as the research concentrated on elementary-level teachers.

Respondents

The respondents were 152 elementary teachers representing the total population of educators in the district for the school year 2020–2021. They were selected through total population sampling, ensuring that all qualified participants were included.

Research Instrument

A two-part survey questionnaire was used. The first part gathered demographic data (age, gender, years in service, and position). The second part measured job satisfaction and school culture, adapted from a study by Cuarto on organizational culture

and job satisfaction (Cuarto, 2014). Teacher performance data were obtained from the Department of Education’s Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) for school year 2019–2020.

Data Gathering Procedure

Approval to conduct the study was obtained from the Schools Division Superintendent and school heads. Data collection was carried out online using Google Forms, with clear instructions to ensure honest and independent responses from participants.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, weighted mean) were used to summarize data on demographics, job satisfaction, school culture, and job performance. Pearson correlation determined the relationships among the main variables, while Chi-square tests examined the association between respondent profiles and their job satisfaction and performance.

Scope and Limitations

The study was limited to elementary teachers in the Ilagan South District during the second semester of the school year 2020–2021. Variables covered were job satisfaction, school culture, and job performance, as measured by specific DepEd IPCRF criteria.

RESULTS

1. What is the profile of the respondents

Table 1
Respondents' Profile

Variables	Category	f	%
Age	19 - 30 (Early Adulthood)	26	17.1
	31 – 50 (Middle Adulthood)	111	73.0
	51 – above (Late Adulthood)	15	9.9
	<i>Total</i>	152	100.0
Sex	Male	20	13.2
	Female	132	86.8
	<i>Total</i>	152	100.0
Years of Service in Public School	1-9 years	70	46.1
	10-18 years	50	32.9
	19-27 years	19	12.5
	28-36 years	9	5.9

	37 years and above	4	2.6
	<i>Total</i>	152	100.0
Position	Teacher III	110	72.4%
	Others	42	27.6%
	<i>Total</i>	152	100.0

The profile of the 152 respondents reveals that the majority are female (86.8%) and fall within the middle adulthood age group of 31–50 years (73.0%), indicating a mature and predominantly female teaching workforce. Most respondents have 1–9 years (46.1%) or 10–18 years (32.9%) of service in public schools, suggesting a relatively early- to mid-career stage. In terms of position, a significant portion (72.4%) hold the rank of Teacher III, reflecting professional growth and experience. These characteristics suggest that the respondents are largely experienced educators who are likely to have well-formed perceptions of organizational culture and job satisfaction, making them suitable participants for the study.

2. What is the level of job satisfaction of the respondents

Table 2
Job Satisfaction Summary

Level of Job Satisfaction	Average Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Work itself	4.56	Very Satisfied
Department of Education (DepEd) Policies and Supervision	4.52	Very Satisfied
Responsibility & Advancement	4.52	Very Satisfied
Interpersonal Relationship	4.51	Very Satisfied
Achievement and Recognition	4.46	Satisfied
Working Condition	4.45	Satisfied
Compensation and Benefits	4.34	Satisfied
Grand Mean	4.48	Satisfied

The respondents' level of job satisfaction is encapsulated in table 2. The table shows that they are most satisfied with their work, which received the highest average weighted mean score of 4.56, followed by responsibility and advancement and DepEd's policies and supervision, both of which received a weighted average of 4.52. The respondents are very satisfied with their interpersonal relationship, with average weighted mean of 4.51. The data further shows that they are satisfied with achievement and recognition, the working condition, and the compensation and benefits, with average weighted mean of 4.46, 4.45, and 4.34, respectively.

The grand mean of 4.48 indicates that the respondents are satisfied with their job. This implies that the respondents feel safe and comfortable in their work. This suggests that the respondents have a positive emotional response and contentment with their job

because they believe their efforts are valued, the policies they are required to follow are just and fair, they find meaning in what they do, and they enjoy working with their co-teachers and supervisors.

3. School Culture in the Workplace

Table 3
School Culture

Dimension	Mean	Description
School Commitment	4.65	Strongly Agree
Goal Clarity	4.59	Strongly Agree
Working Relationship	4.58	Strongly Agree
Management Style	4.57	Strongly Agree
Teacher Participation	4.56	Strongly Agree
Grand Mean	4.59	Strongly Agree

The summary table showing the teachers' perception of the school culture in their workplace is presented in Table 3. The respondents strongly agree to all the statements describing the school culture in the workplaces in terms of School Commitment, Goal Clarity, Working Relationship, Management Style and Teacher Participation as supported by a grand weighted mean of 4.59. This implies that the school culture in the respondents' respective work places is positive, sound, collaborative, engaging, goal-driven, nurturing and rewarding.

4. Level of the Job Performance

Table 4
Job Performance (IPCRF)

Key Result Areas	Mean	Interpretation
Content Knowledge & Pedagogy	4.43	Very Satisfactory
Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners	4.45	Vary Satisfactory
Curriculum and Planning	4.47	Very Satisfactory
Assessment and Reporting	4.48	Very Satisfactory
Plus Factor	4.52	Outstanding
Grand Mean	4.47	Very Satisfactory

Data shows that teachers perform very satisfactory in Content Knowledge & Pedagogy, Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning, Assessment and Reporting as shown in their respective weighted mean. In terms of various related works/activities that contribute to the teaching-learning process or what is called the plus factors, teachers have outstanding performance as shown by the weighted

mean of 4.52. In general, the teachers have very satisfactory performance with a weighted mean of 4.47. This indicates that teachers foster good learning environments that support employee satisfaction, morale, and productivity as well as student learning, fulfillment, and well-being.

5. Do the respondents' profile significantly affect their level of job satisfaction?

a. Age

Table 5
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Respondents' Level of Job Satisfaction and Age Profile

Respondents' Age and their Level of Job Satisfaction along the following areas	Significance of χ^2 or P-value	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Compensation and Benefits	0.4918	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Working Condition	0.3346	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Interpersonal Relationship	0.6004	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
DEPED Policies and Supervision	0.4727	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Achievement and Recognition	0.5272	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Work Itself	0.2044	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Responsibility and Advancement	0.8010	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Table 5 presents the results of the test of significant relationship between the respondents' level of job satisfaction and their age.

The results show that the significance of Chi-square (χ^2) or P-values are greater than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at a 0.05 level of significance which means that there is no significant relationship between the respondents' level of job satisfaction and their age profile. It implies that the age of the respondents does not significantly affect their job satisfaction along the seven areas. It is inferred further that the respondents' level of job satisfaction does not depend on their age.

b. Sex

Table 6
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Respondents' Level of Job Satisfaction and Their Sex Profile

Respondents' Sex and their Level of Job Satisfaction along the following areas	Significance of χ^2 or P-value	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Compensation and Benefits	0.8831	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Working Condition	0.2974	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Interpersonal Relationship	0.2569	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
DEPED Policies and Supervision	0.2219	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Achievement and Recognition	0.0476	$P < 0.05$	Accept H_0	Significant
Work Itself	0.6862	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Responsibility and Advancement	0.1499	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant

The results of the test of significant relationship between the respondents' level of job satisfaction and their sex profile are presented in Table 6.

It is revealed from the results that the significance of χ^2 or the P-values are greater than 0.05 for all the areas except for achievement and recognition. This signifies the acceptance of the null hypothesis at 0.05 significance level. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between the respondents' working conditions, interpersonal relationships, DEPED policies and supervision, work itself, and responsibility and advancement, and their sex profile. It indicates that the teachers' job satisfaction on the mentioned areas does not depend on the respondents' sex profile.

On the other hand, the significance of χ^2 or the P-value is less than 0.05 for achievement and recognition, thus, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 significance level. This implies that there is a significant relationship between the respondents' level of job satisfaction in terms of achievement and recognition and their sex profile, meaning, the respondents' sex profile has significant effect on their achievement and recognition as one of the indicators in their job satisfaction.

c. Years of Teaching Experience in the Government

Table 7
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Respondents' Level of Job Satisfaction and Their Years of Teaching in the Government

Respondents' length of Experience and their Level of Job Satisfaction along the following areas	Significance of χ^2 or P-value	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Compensation and Benefits	0.0023	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Working Condition	0.0464	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Interpersonal Relationship	0.0230	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
DEPED Policies and Supervision	0.1642	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Achievement and Recognition	0.1372	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Work Itself	0.6902	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Responsibility and Advancement	0.1561	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Table 7 displays the result of the test of significant relationships between the respondents' level of job satisfaction and their teaching experience in the government. It is evident from the results that the significance of χ^2 or the P-values are less than 0.05 for compensation and benefits, working condition, and interpersonal relationships. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected 0.05 level of significance which means that there is a significant relationship between the respondents' years of teaching experience in the government and their job satisfaction in terms of compensation benefits, working condition, and interpersonal relationships. It manifests that the longer the teachers' years of teaching experience in the government, the more satisfied are they with their compensation and benefit, working conditions and interpersonal relationship.

However, there is no significant relationship between the respondents' teaching experience in the government and their level of job satisfaction in terms of DepEd policies and supervision, achievement and recognition, work itself, and responsibility and advancement. It implies that the respondents' level of job satisfaction along these areas does not depend on their years of teaching experience in the government. It is further stated that the said variables are independent of each other.

d. Position

Table 8
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Respondents' Level of Job Satisfaction and Their Position

Respondents' Position and their Level of Job Satisfaction along the following areas	Significance of χ^2 or P-value	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Compensation and Benefits	0.0498	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Working Condition	0.1047	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Interpersonal Relationship	0.1932	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
DEPED Policies and Supervision	0.3326	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Achievement and Recognition	0.4607	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Work Itself	0.3549	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Responsibility and Advancement	0.3145	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant

The results of the test of significant relationship between the respondents' level of job satisfaction and their position are displayed in table 8.

The results shows that the significance of χ^2 or the P-values is less than 0.05 for compensation and benefits which implies that there is a significant relationship between the respondents' job satisfaction in terms of compensation and benefits and their position. It implies that the job satisfaction of the respondents in terms of compensation and benefits depends on their position.

However, there is no significant relationship between the respondents' position and their level of job satisfaction in terms of working condition, interpersonal relationship, DepEd policies and supervision, achievement and recognition, work itself, and responsibility and advancement. It means that the respondents' level of job satisfaction in terms of the said areas is independent of their position.

6. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' profile and their level of job performance in terms of?

a. Content knowledge and Pedagogy

Table 9
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Profile and Their Level of Job Performance in Terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy

Respondents' Job Performance in terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy and the following profile variables	Significance of χ^2 or P-value	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Age	0.5443	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Sex	0.0176	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Years of Teaching Experience in the Government	0.3589	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Position	0.3724	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Table 9 exhibits the results of the test of significant relationship between the respondents' profile and their level of job performance in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy.

The results show that the significance of χ^2 or the P-values is less than 0.05 for the sex profile. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is a significant relationship between the respondents' sex profile and their level of job performance in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy. It indicates that the respondents' sex significantly affects their performance in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy.

On the other hand, there is no significant relationship between the respondents' age, years of teaching experience in the government, position, and their level of job performance in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy is not significantly affected by their age, years of teaching experience in government, and position. It means further that the variables are independent from each other.

It is a commonly held belief that men and women perform differently in the teaching profession, but there is limited research to support this claim. While some studies have found that women tend to be better at creating a positive classroom environment and building relationships with students, others have found that men tend to be more effective in promoting academic achievement. However, the evidence is not clear-cut and it is difficult to determine whether gender itself is a determining factor in teacher effectiveness.

b. Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners

Table 10
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Respondents' Profile and Their Level of Job Performance in Terms of Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners

Respondents' Job Performance in terms of Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners and their profile	Significance of x^2 or P-value	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Age	0.2239	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Sex	0.3347	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Years of Teaching Experience in the Government	0.1126	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Position	0.0878	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant

The results of the test of significant relationship between the respondents' profile and their level of job performance in terms of learning environment and diversity of learners are exhibited in Table 10.

It is revealed from the results that the significance of x^2 or the P-values are greater than 0.05. This signifies the acceptance of the null hypothesis at 0.05, hence, there is no significant relationship between the respondents' profile and their level of job performance in terms of learning environment and diversity of learners. The job performance of the respondents in terms of learning environment and diversity of learners does not depend on their age, sex, years of teaching experience in government, and position.

c. Curriculum and Planning

Table 11
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Respondents' Profile and Their Job Performance in Curriculum and Planning

Respondents' Job Performance in terms of Curriculum and Planning and their profile	Significance of x^2 or P-value	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Age	0.9629	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Sex	0.1670	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Years of Teaching Experience in the Government	0.4871	P>0.05	Accept H _o	Not Significant
Position	0.2757	P>0.05	Accept H _o	Not Significant

Table 11 presents the results of the test of significant relationship between the respondents' profile and their level of job performance in terms of curriculum and planning.

The results show that the significance of χ^2 or the P-values are greater than 0.05. For this reason, the null hypothesis is accepted at a 0.05 significance level. As a result, the respondents' profile and their level of job performance in terms of curriculum and planning are not significantly related. Therefore, the age, sex, years of teaching experience in the government, and position of the respondents do not significantly affect their job performance in terms of curriculum and planning.

d. Assessment and Reporting

Table 12
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Respondents' Profile and Their Level of Job Performance in Terms of Assessment and Reporting

Respondents' Job Performance in terms of Assessment and Reporting	Significance of χ^2 or P-value	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Age	0.1912	P>0.05	Accept H _o	Not Significant
Sex	0.3523	P>0.05	Accept H _o	Not Significant
Years of Teaching Experience in the Government	0.4871	P>0.05	Accept H _o	Not Significant
Position	0.3014	P>0.05	Accept H _o	Not Significant

The results of the test of significant relationship between the respondents' profile and their level of job performance in terms of assessment and reporting are presented in Table 12.

The test of relationship yielded an χ^2 or the P-values greater than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at a 0.05 level of significance which implies that there is no significant relationship between the respondents' profile and their level of job performance in terms of assessment and reporting. It implies that the respondents' age, sex, years of teaching experience in the government have no significant effect on their job performance in terms of assessment and reporting.

e. Plus Factor

Table 13
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Respondents' Profile and Their Level of Job Performance in Terms of Plus Factor

Respondents' Job Performance in terms of Plus Factor and their Profile	Significance of χ^2 or P-value	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Age	0.6823	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Sex	0.1793	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Years of Teaching Experience in the Government	0.1472	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Position	0.3586	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Table 13 reflects the results of significant relationship between the respondents' profile and their level of job performance in terms of plus factor.

The results show that the significance of χ^2 or the P-values are greater than 0.05. thereby rejecting the null hypothesis at 0.05 significance level. As a result, there is no significant relationship between the respondents' profile and their level of job performance in terms of plus factor. It indicates that the plus factor as one criterion in the respondents' job performance is not significantly affected by their age, sex, years of teaching experience in the government, and position. It is further inferred that the respondents' profile and the plus factor in their job performance are independent from each other.

7. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' level of job satisfaction and their level of job performance.

Table 14
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Respondents' Level of Job Satisfaction and Their Level of Job Performance

Variables	Computed Value of r	Significance of χ^2 or P-value	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Level of Job Satisfaction and Level of Job Performance	0.6306	0.00089	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant

The results of the test of significant relationship between the respondents' level of job satisfaction and their level of job performance are reflected in Table 14.

It is revealed from the results that the computed value $r=0.6306$ indicates a positive and high relationship between the job satisfaction and job performance of the respondents. The strength of relationship was tested using the significance of r or P -value.

The results show that the significance of r or the P -value. Is less than 0.05. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is significant relationship between respondents' level of job satisfaction and their level of job performance. It implies that the respondents' job satisfaction has significant effect on their job performance. When teachers are satisfied with their job in terms of compensation and benefits, working condition, interpersonal relationship, school policies and supervision, achievement, recognition and work itself, responsibility & advancement, they tend to perform better in their job.

8. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' school culture and their level of job performance?

Table 15
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Respondents' School Culture and their Level of Job Performance

Variables	Computed Value of r	Significance of χ^2 or P -value	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
School Culture and Level of Job Performance	0.5423	0.00095	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant

Table 15 presents the results of the test of significant relationship between the respondents' school culture and their level of job performance.

The computed value of $r=0,5423$ indicates high positive relationship between the respondents' school culture and their level of job performance. The strength and significance of the relationship was tested using the significance of r or the P -value. It is evident from the results that the P -value is less than 0.05. hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 significance level. Thus, there is significant relationship between the school culture and the respondents' level of job performance. It states that the school culture significantly affects their job performance.

DISCUSSION

The demographic profile of the respondents in this study revealed that the majority were female, within the middle adulthood stage (ages 31 to 50), and held the rank of Teacher III. Most had 1 to 18 years of service in public schools. This composition reflects a mature, predominantly female teaching workforce with early to mid-career experience, characteristics similarly observed in the study by Mercado (2019), which emphasized that Filipino teaching professionals, particularly women, are concentrated in public elementary settings. García-Carmona et al. (2019) also documented that teachers within this demographic group commonly exhibit high levels of job resilience despite their susceptibility to work-related stress.

Regarding job satisfaction, the respondents expressed high levels of satisfaction, especially in areas such as their work responsibilities, advancement opportunities, and policy implementation. This finding is consistent with the results of Batugal and Tindowen (2019), who concluded that a positive perception of internal policies and professional growth enhances job satisfaction. Similarly, Putra and Triatmanto (2020) underscored the influence of intrinsic motivators such as meaningful work and responsibility on both satisfaction and performance outcomes. Manalo et al. (2020) further supported the idea that satisfaction is driven by perceived fairness and recognition in organizational settings.

Respondents also indicated a strong agreement with the presence of a positive school culture, marked by clarity of goals, supportive relationships, collaborative management, and shared commitment. This finding is reinforced by Cabigao (2019), who argued that supportive leadership and a strong culture enhance school performance and teacher engagement. Likewise, Lapian et al. (2020) established that a healthy school culture positively influences teachers' organizational behavior and morale.

The performance of teachers was rated as very satisfactory, especially in areas like content knowledge, pedagogy, planning, and assessment. Furthermore, their participation in broader school-related activities, commonly referred to as plus factors, was evaluated as outstanding. These findings align with Al-Shammari et al. (2021), who found that highly satisfied teachers tend to demonstrate better instructional practices and school involvement. Aliazas and Elisa (2021) similarly emphasized that institutional work culture, when rooted in support and professional development, leads to elevated levels of productivity among teachers.

When exploring the relationship between job satisfaction and demographic characteristics such as age, no significant relationship was found. This contrasts with Kadlong et al. (2017), who found age-related variations in job satisfaction among Region XII teachers. However, the finding is supported by García-Carmona et al. (2019), who noted that although age may be linked to burnout, it does not reliably predict job satisfaction across cultures.

Gender was not a significant factor in most areas of job satisfaction, except for achievement and recognition, where a significant relationship was identified. This partially

supports Mercado (2019), who suggested that female educators value recognition more highly than their male counterparts. Conversely, Putra and Triatmanto (2020) argued that structural and organizational factors, not gender, are primary determinants of satisfaction, lending partial support to this study's findings.

Teaching experience was found to be a significant predictor of satisfaction in terms of compensation, working conditions, and interpersonal relationships. Manalo et al. (2020) and Lapian et al. (2020) both identified experience as a mediating factor that enhances appreciation of institutional support systems and social workplace dynamics.

With regard to position, significant relationships were observed only for satisfaction with compensation and benefits. Higher-ranking positions were associated with increased satisfaction in this area. This finding aligns with Batugal and Tindowen (2019) and Al-Shammari et al. (2021), both of whom observed that professional rank can enhance material benefits but has limited impact on interpersonal or intrinsic dimensions of satisfaction.

Notably, gender significantly affected teacher performance in content knowledge and pedagogy, with female teachers performing better in this domain. This supports García-Carmona et al. (2019), who reported that female educators tend to excel in nurturing instructional environments. However, the results contrast with Aliazas and Elisa (2021), who found no significant performance differences by gender in Philippine public schools.

No significant relationship was found between any aspect of teacher profile such as age, sex, experience, or position and performance in areas such as learning environment, curriculum and planning, assessment and reporting, or plus factors. These findings are consistent with Cabigao (2019) and Putra and Triatmanto (2020), who emphasized that performance is more strongly influenced by institutional support and professional culture than by demographic variables.

The study found a high and statistically significant positive relationship between job satisfaction and teacher performance. This result is well-supported across both local and international literature. Batugal and Tindowen (2019), Manalo et al. (2020), and Putra and Triatmanto (2020) all established that high job satisfaction significantly enhances professional effectiveness and commitment. Al-Shammari et al. (2021) also concluded that satisfied teachers are more engaged, motivated, and productive.

Similarly, a significant positive relationship was found between school culture and teacher performance. This supports the assertions of Cabigao (2019), who stressed that shared leadership and organizational culture directly impact teacher efficacy. The same conclusion was echoed in the work of Lapian et al. (2020) and Aliazas and Elisa (2021), both of whom emphasized that culture-driven school environments foster professional excellence.

The results of this study confirm the critical role of job satisfaction and school culture in shaping teacher performance. Most findings are consistent with previous literature, both local and international, highlighting the universal importance of supportive environments, fair compensation, professional development, and collaborative culture in education systems.

While a few inconsistencies emerged, particularly in the impact of age and gender, these may be due to contextual differences and warrant further exploration. The findings reinforce the need for education leaders and policymakers to create systems that invest in teacher well-being, empowerment, and recognition as strategic tools for enhancing school outcomes.

Conclusions

1. School culture is a vital component in ensuring that teachers are satisfied with their work do well in their jobs. A sound school culture results to a positive outlook and high level of job satisfaction and relationship among teachers and staff and a very satisfactory job performance.
2. The respondents expressed strong satisfaction with the nature of their work, the responsibility given to them, and the advancement opportunities provided by the school, the clarity of the Department of Education's policies and supervision, and their interpersonal relationships with their coworkers and supervisors. The research also shows that respondents are content with the school's achievement and recognition, their working conditions, and the remuneration and benefits they receive from their jobs.
3. The respondents' school community demonstrates dedication, objective clarity, solid working relationships, a collaborative management approach, and teacher participation.
4. Teachers' job satisfaction is not affected by their age, sex, years of teaching experience, or teaching position.
5. The teachers' sex affects how they perform in their jobs.

Recommendations

1. DepEd needs to review the regulations governing achievement and recognition, as well as the perks and compensation given to the teachers. School administrators must provide a more welcoming environment by improving the working conditions or the physical amenities.
2. The school administration must sustain the positive school culture by encouraging more open communication of ideas and innovation, establishing fun traditions and rituals, engaging the teachers and students in beneficial ways outside of instruction time, and reviewing and adjusting the pillars of the school.
3. Professional development for teachers must be enhanced to ensure continued excellent service delivery.

4. The government should establish a centralized loan processing system for government employees to streamline the application and approval process for loans. This system should have a secure and transparent database that stores employee information and loan records, and allows for efficient tracking of loan applications and disbursements.
5. The government should prioritize investment in technical facilities in public schools to improve the quality of education and enhance students' learning experiences. This investment should focus on providing schools with updated technology, such as computers, internet access, and multimedia equipment, to support the integration of technology into the curriculum and provide students with access to digital resources.
6. The school heads should regularly express their appreciation and recognition to teachers and staff for their hard work and dedication to the school and students. This appreciation can be given in various forms, such as verbal praise, written notes, or awards. By doing so, school heads can help to create a positive and supportive work environment, boost morale, and retain high-quality teachers and staff. Furthermore, appreciation and recognition can help to improve job satisfaction, motivation, and performance among teachers and staff, leading to better educational outcomes for students.
7. The school and educational authorities should ensure that teachers have easy access to relevant policies and guidelines. This can be achieved by creating an online platform or database that houses all relevant policies and procedures, and making it accessible to all teachers
8. School and educational supervisors should be equipped with strong leadership skills to effectively lead and manage their teams. This includes skills such as effective communication, problem-solving, decision-making, and the ability to inspire and motivate others.
9. Schools and educational institutions should establish a formal program for recognizing and rewarding the achievements of teachers and staff members. This program should include regular opportunities for teachers and staff to be recognized for their hard work, dedication, and contributions to the school and students. A formal recognition program can help to boost morale, improve job satisfaction, and motivate teachers and staff to continue to excel in their roles. It can also promote a positive and supportive work environment and encourage collaboration and teamwork among colleagues
10. School management should ensure that the roles and responsibilities of all teachers, staff members, and administrators are clearly defined and communicated. This includes providing clear job descriptions, outlining expectations and responsibilities, and providing regular training and development opportunities. By doing so, school management can avoid confusion and overlap in roles and responsibilities, leading to a more organized and effective educational system.
11. The role of teachers in education is crucial and they should be given the necessary freedom and authority to perform their duties effectively. Sufficient freedom and authority will enable teachers to make informed decisions, utilize their expertise and creativity, and foster a positive learning environment.

12. The school managements should adopt a proactive approach to conflict resolution through direct confrontation and setting disagreements rather than avoiding or ignoring them. Conflicts and disagreements are inevitable in any organizational setting, but addressing them directly and transparently can lead to timely and mutually beneficial solutions.
13. Teachers need to be continuously updated with new teaching strategies and methodologies. Professional development opportunities can help teachers learn new techniques for promoting critical and creative thinking and higher order thinking.
14. Teachers need to be equipped with the knowledge and skills to create inclusive learning environments. Providing diversity and inclusion training can help teachers understand the importance of diversity and develop strategies for promoting inclusiveness in the classroom.
15. Teachers need to be equipped with the knowledge and skills to effectively plan, manage, and implement developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes. Providing professional development opportunities can help teachers stay current with best practices and new techniques.
16. Teachers need to be equipped with the knowledge and skills to effectively assess and report student learning. Providing professional development opportunities can help teachers stay current with best practices and new techniques for assessment and reporting.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher adhered strictly to ethical research guidelines. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents, with the assurance that participation was voluntary and withdrawal was allowed at any stage. Anonymity and confidentiality were preserved throughout the study. Data privacy laws and institutional research protocols were followed. No conflict of interest was present in the execution or reporting of this study.

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